

A MACHINE LEARNING APPROACH TO THE DESIGN OF CUSTOMIZED SHOE LASTS

BRIAN G. BOOTH¹ JAN SIJBERS¹ TOON HUYSMANS^{1,2}

¹UNIVERSITY OF ANTWERP ²DELFT UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY
<http://cadwalk.eu> EMAIL: brian.booth@uantwerpen.be

OBJECTIVE

The purpose of this pilot study was to evaluate whether machine learning algorithms can be used to design custom shoe lasts in an accurate fashion (i.e. with sub-millimeter error).

If a machine learning approach is possible, then it might be able to reduce the time and effort required to design custom shoe lasts.

MATERIALS

- 70 orthopedic shoe users were recruited through a partner company (De Prêtre Orthopedie).
- Both feet from each user were scanned using an Elinvision FootIn3D laser 3D foot scanner.
- Each user had custom shoe lasts hand designed and made by the partner company.
- The shoe lasts were also scanned using the same Elinvision FootIn3D scanner.

METHODS

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

- Average prediction error roughly 10% of the last measurement's range.
- Average geometric error is 3.02 mm.
- Presence of outlier results indicates the need for more training data.
- Large errors near toes and ankle as shoe style was not considered in this study.
- Overall, this technique shows potential. Future work includes more data collection and the inclusion of shoe styles in the machine learning framework.

REFERENCES

- [1] Stanković, K., Booth, B.G., Danckaers, F., Burg, F., Vermaelen, P., Duerinck, S., Sijbers, J., Huysmans, T. (2018) Three-dimensional quantitative analysis of healthy foot shape: a proof of concept study, *Journal of Foot and Ankle Research*, 11(8).
- [2] Ma, X. & Luximon, A. (2013) Design and manufacture of shoe lasts. In A. Luximon (Ed.), *Handbook of Footwear Design and Manufacture* (pp. 177-196). Woodhead Publishing.